

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF SURFACE MODIFICATION OF TA2 USING MICRO-BEAM PLASMA ARC

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ABSTRACT

The surface remelting was performed on commercial pure titanium TA2 using micro-beam plasma arc (MPA) under 3 working conditions, i.e. remelting without cooling water, remelting one time with cooling water and remelting two times with cooling water. The surface topography, microstructure and microhardness distribution along surface layer of TA2 pure titanium by different techniques of MPA were investigated by optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction and Vickers' microhardness tester, respectively. The results show that the characterization of acicular martensite could be acquired after MPA under 3 working conditions mainly owing to α' phase formation during rapid cooling by MPA remelting. There were no microcracks or impurities, furthermore, there were also no phase transformation but the dislocations in the 3 treated samples, which was scanned using the MPA under 3 working conditions. X-ray diffraction results indicated that the surface remelting layer composed of single phase which was similar to the substrate. The microhardness of the 3 treated samples was significantly improved as compared with the untreated substrates. Especially, the sample remelted 2 times with cooling water, the microhardness of the surface was improved to about 500 HV_{0.3}, the microhardness of the sample remelted 1 time with cooling water was improved to 470 HV_{0.3} while the microhardness of the sample remelted without cooling water was improved to 430 HV_{0.3} from about 190HV_{0.3} of the untreated sample. The remelting and fine-grain microstructure of surface layer caused by MPA were the main polishing mechanism and the reason of modification of surface topography and the increment microhardness was mainly due to the dislocations and fine grains in the modified layer induced by MPA. Preliminary electrochemical studies have indicated the sample remelted 1 time with cooling water exhibits excellent corrosion resistance in 0.5 M NaCl solutions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Owing to high strength to weight ratio, excellent corrosion resistance and biocompatibility and so on desired performance, Ti alloys became popular for various machinery, transportation systems, as well as biomedical field, especially in power system and desalinization plants in recent years [1-3]. However, due to the intrinsic properties of titanium and its alloys so poor wear resistance that further improvement is still desirable for some applications such as TA2 using for condenser [4, 5]. Surface modification is an effective way to improve the properties of materials and thus extend their application range in tougher environments [4-6]. Especially, surface remelting, using a high power beam to melt the surface of workpiece (or sample) to obtain a layer of fine martensite, has been

actively investigated and applied to improve wear and corrosion properties[6]. It is generally believed laser beam still attract much attention for their application as source of directed energy. Langlade et al [7], Pérez[8], Lavissee et al. [9] T.M. Yue[10] investigated and applied laser surface remelting to improve wear and corrosion resistance properties for Ti alloys. At present, the main problems in laser cladding and alloying are still the cracks, which result from the very high cooling rate of the melted pool after laser beam movement, the poor result reproducibility, the relatively low energy transfer and fairly high maintenance and equipment cost [4].

Compared to laser beam, Micro-beam Plasma arc (MPA) possesses advantages of a series of satisfying performance: 10000~50000°C, $10^5\sim 10^6\text{W/cm}^2$ of energy density, relatively inexpensive cost, simple structure, easy alignment and easy operation [11]. So it is reasonable that MPA is applied as the heating source. Although MPA surface remelting have been actively investigated and applied to improve wear and corrosion properties for various steels alloys [11], there is little reported on this subject with titanium alloys in the literature. The surface changes caused by MPA have been less investigated. The objective of the this paper is to study the effect of MPA surface remelting on the development of the microstructure and improving surface performance of pure titanium(TA2) pipe.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The substrate material used for the experiments was the pipe-like specimen of the industry pure titanium (TA2) with outer diameter of 32 mm, thickness of 3 mm and length of 150 mm with a chemical composition as shown in Table 1. The microscopic structure of the the untreated TA2 pipe primarily possessed equiaxial α phase micro-structure with grain size of about 20 μm as shown in Fig.1. Fig.2. is the schematic picture of MPA remelting with auxiliary cooling system, the pipe-like specimen for scanning by LHW-50 inverter pulse type micro-beam plasma welding units under 3 working conditions, i.e. remelting without cooling water, remelting one time with cooling water and remelting two times with cooling water. Before scanning by a micro-beam plasma arc, the surfaces of the specimen were cleaned with acetone, abraded by 500 μm grit paper and polished with alumina paste. Due to the high chemical activity of Ti alloys, in the scanning treatment pure argon (99.99%) was used as shielding gas, the plasma nozzle was used as the cathode and the specimen as the anode. For contrast, the process parameters of remelting treatment under 3 working condition were uniform with the following parameter: The plasma-arc current $I=45\text{ A}$, plasma-arc voltage $U=19\text{ V}$, scanning velocity $V=3\text{ mm/s}$ and plasma-arc beam diameter $D=1.5\text{ mm}$. the plasma-arc tracks with a 50% overlap were melted on the surface of the specimen.

Table 1 Chemical composition of commercial TA2 (wt.%)

Ti	H	Fe	C	O	N
balance	0.01max	0.3max	0.1max	0.25max	0.05max

The phase, microstructure, hardness of the specimens and chemical composition were characterized and analysed by optical microscopy(OM), scanning electron microscopy(SEM), X-ray diffraction(XRD). As a result of strong corrosion resistance[11] , The polished specimens were chemically etched in a solution of 20mlHF, 30ml HNO₃ and 50 ml H₂O for a period of 1 min. Furthermore, micro-hardness test were taken mainly on transverse sections with a load of 300g for 15s.

Fig 1. Microstructure of the untreated TA2

Fig.2. the schematic picture of MPA remelting with auxiliary cooling system

(1)soldering gun; (2) remelting layer; (3) TA2 pipe; (4) cooling water inlet; (5) cooling water outlet;

The surface corrosion resistance of the MPA treated samples was assessed by means of the electrochemical polarization tests which were carried out using an electrochemical workstation (CHI660) at room temperature by the conventional three-electrode cell including the test specimen as the work electrode, a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode and a large-area platinum flat electrode as the counter electrode configuration. The treated specimens which only one treated surface by MPA was exposed to the electrolyte and the other surfaces were covered with epoxy resin were completely immersed into a beaker containing 200 ml of 0.5M NaCl solution prepared with analytical grade reagent and distilled water under open air environment. For comparison, an untreated TA2 sample was also prepared under the same experimental conditions. The tested parameters are: the exposure area of the test surface of the specimen 1 cm², the scan rate 0.5mV/s. The polarization measurements were made after stabilizing the sample at the open circuit potential for at least 30 min. Finally, the Tafel extrapolation was able to predict the corrosion current density and corrosion potential.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The exterior feature of the MPA treated TA2 specimen under 2 working conditions (remelting one time with cooling water and remelting two times with cooling water) is shown in the macrograph of Fig. 3. A shiny gold color was observed on the surface specimen remelted 2 times with cooling water, while the color of the specimen remelted 1 time with cooling water was shiny blue. From visual inspection, more sleek appearance, formation on the MPA processed under 2 working conditions tracks was observed throughout the top surface compared with the surface before the treatment. No matter what working conditions, surfaces of remelting were relatively smooth and were free from any forms of surface cracking.

Fig. 3. Photograph of the surface state of MPA treated TA2 pipe

Fig.4. Cross-sectional SEM morphology of specimen with different MPA treated methods:(a)remelting without cooling water; (b)remelting one time with cooling water; (c) remelting two times with cooling water

The photographs of the cross-sectional morphology treated specimens are shown in Fig.4. After remelting, solidification began with epitaxial growth on the substrate, which produced a layer. Three different remelting conditions were compared, namely remelting without cooling water, remelting one time with cooling water (i.e. the increase of solidification rates) and remelting two times with cooling water(i.e. the increase of energy input), resulting in the melt pool width of About 1.55, 1.2 and 1.4 mm,

respectively. They showed a very dense structure with pronounced basal plane orientation. It can be seen that the remelting depth differs significantly between remelting zone produced by the 2 treated methods due to the difference in energy input, the depth of modified surface layer increased with the increase of energy input when the sample was treated under water cooling condition, as presented in Fig. 4b, c. On the other hand, with the cooling speed decreasing, the depth of modified surface layer was increased when the sample was treated by the same set parameters (see Fig. 4a, b). The change of the grains morphology in the modified layers indicated that MPA processing parameters significantly affect the microstructure. From these micrographs we can see that the β equiaxed grains all decrease in size along the depth of the alloyed layers with different MPA treated methods.

Fig. 5 optical micrographs of specimens with different MPA treated methods: (a), (d), (g) remelting without cooling water; (b), (e), (h) remelting one time with cooling water; (c), (f), (i) remelting two times with cooling water

Fig. 5 shows the microstructures in TA2 substrate, the heat affected zone and the remelted zone for samples. It can be seen that single α phase in the base metal has been changed to acicular α -prime (α') martensite. According Ref. [12], after remelting, due to the high temperature gradients, the material in remelted zone (RZ) has undergone the remelting and resolidification, while the material in the heat affected zone (HAZ) has only undergone heating and cooling process with no melting involved. Vertically, It was found that the cross section of remelted TA2 appear zones which were in turn remelted zone (RZ), heat affected zone (HAZ) and substrate, the micro-structure of samples produced by MPA will differ in the 3 zones (RZ, HAZ and substrate), respectively. The optical micrographs (Fig. 5) indicated that elongated acicular structure was observed at the top of the layer (Fig. 5a, b, c). Away from the RZ, the structure became coarser (Fig. 5d, e, f), which can be attributed to the grains will grow epitaxially [13]. This is believed to be due to only subjected to the heating and cooling process with no melting involve. From these micrographs, Due to the high energy input, the

dark zones that indicated the melt pool boundaries were intense (Fig. 5a, b, c). The width of RZ of sample remelting without cooling water (Fig. 5a) was 600 μm , as expected. The width of RZ was 400 μm and 620 μm when remelting one time (Fig. 5b) and two times with cooling water (Fig. 5c), respectively. Similarly, the energy input and solidification rates would influence the width of HAZ. At optimized parameters, the width of HAZ was approximately 950 μm (Fig. 5d, g) for the sample remelting without cooling water, 800 μm (Fig. 5e, h) for the sample remelting one time with cooling water and 780 μm (Fig. 5f, i) for the sample remelting two times with cooling water, respectively. It is discovered that the melt pool width (including RZ and HAZ) was not influenced significantly by increasing in energy input (compare the sample remelting two times with the sample remelting one time). With greater solidification rates, the sample remelting with cooling water achieved a thinner hardened layer (including RZ and HAZ) than the sample remelting without cooling water.

Fig.6 Micrographs of specimens with different MPA treated methods at the top of remelting layer (pictured left) and the middle of remelting layer (pictured right): (a),(b) remelting without cooling water; (c),(d) remelting one time with cooling water; (e),(f) remelting two times with cooling water

Fig. 6 further shows the typical acicular martensite formed in the RZ by MPA remelting. This fine, acicular martensitic product exhibits a hexagonal close-packed crystal structure and possesses high hardness, but relatively low ductility and toughness [14]. At higher magnification view, the newly formed layers in the middle of remelting layer showed a subtle net-like structure consisting of short micro-rods (Fig.6).

Due to the different energy input and cooling rate, the distinct microstructure of the sample produced by MPA would differ in the three working condition. Fig. 6a-f presents Micrographs of

specimens with different MPA treated methods at the top and middle of remelting layer, respectively, as expected due to the high temperature gradients that occur during the MPA process, the present phase was a very fine acicular martensite [15]. At the top of remelting layer (Fig. 6a, c, e) elongated grains appeared more or less along the building direction with heights of the order of 20~30 μm . It is found that the elongated grains were oriented towards the molten pool and appear more or less along the scanning direction. The present phase was fine acicular martensitic phase, or the fresh α' phase with inclination towards the building and the direction of the grains at the top of layers were almost parallel to each another. They were diagonally aligned. As shown in Fig. 6, the angle of slope of the elongated grains relied on the energy input: the higher the energy input, the higher the slope angle. When remelting two times with cooling water, the angle was 90° and the elongated grains were aligned vertically. The growth direction of the grains at the RZ was perpendicular to the back of the melt pool. With this high cooling rate dramatic microstructural changes in the melted zone can be expected. Specifically, the use of air cooling (without water cooling) resulted in the formation of a primarily α' phase consisting of subtle net-like structure (Fig. 6a). In contrast, the use of water cooling produced a fine-grained, dense microstructure consisting exclusively of α' phase (Fig. 6c). However, the sample remelted two times using cooling water (Fig. 6e) was primarily fine-grained, dense acicular martensitic which were almost parallel to each another and oriented towards the molten at the top of layers.

As for the middle of remelting layer, the temperature of melting pool decreased obviously with the increase of distance from the MPA heat source. There were elongated acicular grains with various kinds of orientation which intersect with each another to form a dense grid plan in the middle of remelting layer (Fig. 6b, d, f). In addition, particles and particle spacing in the sample remelting one time with cooling water which were much finer than those in the sample remelting without cooling water due to higher cooling rate. The sizes of fine acicular structure and particle spacing ranging in size from 0.5 to $1\mu\text{m}$ were observed (Fig. 6b), whereas the sizes of fine acicular structure and particle spacing ranged from 0.1 to $0.5\mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 6d). Furthermore, the sample remelting two times with cooling water (Fig. 6f) showed a much denser structure than those of aforementioned 2 samples.

Fig.7. Microhardness profile on cross-section of specimens with different MPA treated methods

Fig.7 indicates the microhardness distributions along surface layer for MPA scanning treated specimens. It is noted that the MPA scanning treated specimens exhibit a graded distribution of hardness. This trend was clearly apparent for all MPA scanning treated specimens. In addition, it can be observed that the original TA2 pure titanium has an average microhardness of approximately $190\text{HV}_{0.3}$. After MPA remelting, the surface hardness and the value of the maximum hardness for these samples was improved with the increasing solidification rate and energy input, as illustrated in

Fig. 6. When remelting 2 times with cooling water, both the surface microhardness (average value $460\text{HV}_{0.3}$ increases by 2.3 times) and the maximum microhardness ($509\text{HV}_{0.3}$) were the maximum; When remelting one time with cooling water, both the surface microhardness (average value $430\text{HV}_{0.3}$ increases by 2.1 times) and the maximum microhardness ($471\text{HV}_{0.3}$) were the next; when remelting without cooling water, both the surface microhardness (average value $390\text{HV}_{0.3}$ increases by 1.9 times) and the maximum microhardness ($433\text{HV}_{0.3}$) were the minimum. It reveals that due to higher solidification rate than the sample remelted without water cooling, the sample remelted with water cooling got higher micro-hardness. On the other hand, It also revealed that due to higher energy input than the sample remelted one time, the sample remelted 2 times got higher micro-hardness.

Compared with the original untreated TA2, owing to the presence of acicular martensitic phase, or the α' phase, which was hexagonally packed as well as the formation of pronounced compact and homogenous microstructure, the MPA scanning treated specimens exhibited higher hardness than the substrate of the TA2. The designs of cooling water and remelting two times for MPA should be beneficial to increase the hardness of the coatings. Moreover, the depth of modified surface layer increased with the increase of energy input, as presented in Fig.7. Therefore, the hardness of TA2 pure titanium was mainly related to the fine grain/subgrain and/or the dislocations induced by MPA. The increased hardness was obtained due to the microstructural changes caused by rapid solidification owing to the self-quenching effect of the substrate after MPA remelting.

Fig.8. XRD patterns with different treated methods.

The phase of the remelting layers formed by the different MPA treated process was characterized by XRD analysis, as shown in Figs.8. XRD results indicated that the original TA2 pure titanium without MPA scanning has only one phase of α -Ti. After MPA scanning, the phase of TA2 specimen MPA-treated was the same as prior to MPA-treated. There was also only one phase of α for the MPA

remelted specimens and no other new phase induced. It can be seen that the width of peak was increased with 3 different MPA treated process in turn, to remelt 2 times with cooling water was the widest ; to remelt one time with cooling water was the next; follow to remelt without cooling water. While the intensity of peak was decreased with 3 different MPA treated process in turn, to remelt without cooling water was the longest; to remelt one time with cooling water was the next; follow to remelt 2 times with cooling water. Especially, the (101) peak position with a low symmetric broadening and a decreasing in its intensity with different treated methods respectively can readily be observed in Figs. 8, and the (002) peak almost completely disappeared when the sample was remelted 2 times with cooling water. This should be related to the increased dislocations and the formations of some fine subgrains in virtue of cooling rate and energy input.

Fig.9. Polarized curve of the pure titanium with different treated methods in NaCl solution

Table2. corrosion potential and current density for specimens with different MPA treated methods and untreated TA2(sample 1 remelting without cooling water; sample 2 remelting one time with cooling water; sample 3 untreated TA2; sample 4 remelting two times with cooling water)

sample	1	2	3	4
$I_{corr}, A/cm^2$	3.116×10^{-8}	6.186×10^{-8}	7.022×10^{-8}	6.862×10^{-6}
E_{corr}, V	-0.793	-0.452	-0.935	-0.302

The results of the polarization test for pure titanium with different treated methods in 0.5M NaCl solution at 37 °C were displayed in Fig.9. Table 2 lists the corrosion current density and the corrosion potential of the MPA treated sample and untreated TA2 calculated from the intersection of the

cathodic and anodic Tafel curves by using the Tafel extrapolation method. It can be seen from Table 2 that the sample remelted by MPA without cooling water has lower corrosion current density (3.116×10^{-8}) than that of untreated TA2 (7.022×10^{-8}); the sample remelted one time by MPA with cooling water has become much closer corrosion current density (6.186×10^{-8}) than that of untreated TA2 (7.022×10^{-8}) and the sample remelted 2 times by MPA with cooling water has been on the increase (6.862×10^{-6}) instead of on the decrease. Namely, after MPA remelting, the corrosion current density showed little change. It should be noted that the value of surface roughness gets to being increased with improving pulsed energy density and/or pulse duration, and/or number of irradiation pulses. Compared with the untreated specimens, the MPA remelting specimens has good corrosion resistance. By using the data in Table 2 it can be observed that when the sample was remelted 2 times by MPA with cooling water, due to higher energy input, the porosity in specimen surface would be increased, and this finally leads to increase in corrosion rate. The E_{corr} of the sample remelted by MPA with two times cooling water, the sample remelted by MPA with one time cooling water and the sample remelted by MPA without cooling water were $-0.302V$, $-0.452V$ and $-0.793V$, respectively, which showed a positive shift compared to the $-0.935V$ of the untreated TA2. The more positive E_{corr} of the sample remelted by MPA indicated that they possessed better corrosion resistance than untreated TA2. The excellent corrosion resistance of MPA remelting treated attributes to the formation of protective net-like structure (mainly α' phase). With elongated acicular structure in the surface, Ti ions in the substrate would have less chance to react with the corrosion media, and dissolution of metal ions in the NaCl solution could be limited. In conclusion, compared with the sample remelted 2 times with cooling water and the sample remelted without cooling water, the sample remelted 1 time with cooling water has much better corrosion resistance. From the point of view of energy-saving and corrosion-resistance of the material, it won't be necessary to remelt TA2 alloy 2 times.

4 CONCLUSION

As is well known remelting with cooling water may produce an even higher cooling rate, while remelting 2 times with cooling water may obtain higher energy input.

From the present investigation, the following conclusions may be drawn:

(1) Micro-beam plasma-arc scanning is a simple and very effective method of surface modification to enhance the micro-hardness of alloys. The top surface of the material may be melted/remelted by this process and solidified rapidly by the self-quenching of substrate.

(2) Micro-beam plasma-arc surface treatment of TA2 alloy produced a relatively smooth and crack-free modified surface layer. From this experiment we can therefore conclude that: the distinct microstructure of the sample produced by MPA differ in the three working condition due to the different energy input and cooling rate; the subtle net-like structure was observed at the top of layers after MPA remelted without cooling water and remelted 1 time with cooling water; the dense acicular martensitic which were almost parallel to each another and oriented towards the molten at the top of layers after MPA remelted 2 times with cooling water.

(3) The microhardness of the remelting zone were enhanced to $390 HV_{0.3}$, $430 HV_{0.3}$ and $460 HV_{0.3}$ after micro-beam plasma-arc treatment without cooling water, remelted 1 time by MPA with cooling water and remelted 2 times by MPA with cooling water, respectively. The improvement is considered to be primarily due to the grain refining and recrystallization by rapid solidification.

(4) Compared with the untreated specimens, the MPA remelted specimens have good corrosion resistance. Especially, the sample remelted 1 time by MPA with cooling water has lower corrosion current density (3.116×10^{-8}) and higher corrosion current density ($-0.452V$) than that of untreated TA2 (7.022×10^{-8} and $-0.935V$)

The present study clearly demonstrates that MPA surface remelting 1 time with cooling water can be a more potential way to improve corrosion resistance and pitting potential of titanium and thus to enlarge its application range in harsher environments.

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